

Research Article

Factors Influencing Rural Youth Adoption of Cassava Recommended Production Practices in Onu-Imo Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The broad objective of the study was to determine the factors influencing rural youth adoption of cassava recommended production practices in Onu-Imo Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: describe the socio-economic characteristics and institutional variables affecting rural youth involved in cassava production activities; determine the level of adoption of recommended cassava production practices by rural youth in Onu-Imo Local Government Area and their effects; identify the factors influencing rural youth adoption of recommended cassava production practices. Data for the study were collected using structured questionnaire administered to 120 rural youth cassava producers. Four communities were purposively sampled based on their rurality and intensity in cassava production. About 10 percent of the rural youth cassava farmers were randomly selected from each village. The analytical tools employed were percentages, ranking, correlation and regression analysis. Results show that the level of adoption of the recommended cassava production practices was high. Findings of the study reveal that 40percent of the respondents adopted planting healthy stems cut at midpoint while moderate to high level of adoption was found for five other recommended production practices (planting time, plant spacing, planting on ridges, weeding time and fertilizer application). The determinants of adoption were: age, gender, marital status, education, farm size, house hold size, farming experience, amount of credit received, extension contact, and membership of cooperative societies, yield and income. Both correlation and regression coefficients were found to be significant for household size, extension contact, yield and income. Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that credit should be made available to youth cassava farmers to enable them remain in business. Efforts should be made to introduce modern processing equipment (technology) to cassava producers. This will go a long way to reduce wastage. Furthermore, policy measures that would guarantee increase in yield and farm income of the rural youth involved in cassava production as well as provide cost effective inputs is recommended, as this will invariably improve rural livelihood and food security of the nation.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture plays an important role in employment and revenue generation as well as in the provision of raw materials for industrial development. Food production seems to be declining over the years while the population keeps growing. Hence, with rapid increase in population growth, the gap between food demand and supply continues to widen in Nigeria (Ijere, 1992; Ugwoke *et al.*, 2005). Agriculture remains a family enterprise in Nigeria, as youth, women and men of all ages are involved one way or the other in the agricultural production process. The implication raised by this is that, concerted effort by everybody capable of potential contribution(s) to the agricultural development process is required, if Nigeria is to make a realistic and positive step in solving its agricultural problems (Akinola and Akindiji, 1991; Ekong, 2003).

The youths on the other hand, constitute the most important sector in any society. They serve as channels for the transmission of culture and the perpetuation of recognizable identity (Akinbode, 1991; Ekong, 2003). They also provide the manpower for the socio-economic development of the society. In the rural sector, youths provide opportunities for generating farming entrepreneurs and other rural professions. In addition, rural youths enjoy certain life experiences, which can be considered advantageous. These include a greater frequency of interaction with family, and hence less emotional problems. They also enjoy earlier and greater involvement in work roles, and have opportunity of becoming economically independent earlier than their urban counterparts (Akinbode, 1991; Eremie, 2002). Furthermore, the rural youth contributes to family labour, they also constitute a moving force in the development of their communities.

Arokoyo (1992) and Ekong (2003), noted that the youths who have the energy to take up agricultural production do not believe or have the knowledge that agricultural production can really be a profitable venture. Thus, there is urgent need to educate youths to know the importance and prospects in farming and take to it, thereby increasing the farming population. More so, the youth need to appreciate the role of agriculture, stay back in the villages where there are abundant resources and make use of what they have in productive activities. This will really support the extension workers, who are already short in number compared to the farmers that have to be reached (Eremie, 2002).

The current challenges in development are so demanding that only the participation of people who are energetic, creative, innovative, productive and committed who could bring development, should they all be mobilized. (Arokoyo, 1992; Mgbada, 2000; Solanke, 2004). These attributes which are critical to growth and development are substantially discernable in the youth. Thus, they constitute the major resource base for any country that wants to embark on any meaningful agricultural and rural development.

Cassava often referred to as "poor man crop" is an important staple food in the tropics (IITA, 1992) and

plays a major role in alleviating the African food crisis (Hahn, 1997). Cassava produces acceptable yields on poor depleted soils where other crops will yield virtually nothing, therefore it can be used to take advantage of marginal soils (Alabi and Alabi, 2002). It has become the most important root crop in tropical Africa providing food for over 200 million people (IITA, 1992). Almost all the cassava produced is used for human consumption and less than 5% is used as industrial raw materials (Ajayi and Onuche, 2005). Rural youths play a central role in cassava production, processing and marketing. They are responsible for cassava production which provides additional income earning opportunities, and enhances their ability to contribute to household food security (Ojuekaiye, 2001).

Increased production of staple food crops, such as cassava, can not be achieved by the use of traditional production practices alone. It requires more efficient production technologies to cope with the demand for cassava products both for consumption and non-consumption (Adeolu, 1990). According to Nweke *et al.* (2002), eighty percent of Nigerians in the rural areas eat a cassava meal at least once a day; hence it plays a major role in the country's food security. The high consumption of cassava in the country, led to an increase in the demand for this crop both for food and industrial uses, which exceeded the supply (Odigboh, 1985). Further more, cassava production is labour intensive; this is worsened by scarcity and high cost of hired labour especially when there is need to expand cassava production beyond subsistence level.

In order to reverse this trend, government and agricultural research institutes have demonstrated that increasing the food needs of the country, can be met by introducing improved crop production practices to farmers (PNADP, 1997). Cassava, the most widely grown root crop and staple food of most Nigerians has featured predominantly among the improved crop varieties that have been disseminated to farmers (PNADP, 1997).

Cassava has for a long time has been a versatile staple food crop for the people of Onu-Imo Local Government Area of Imo State. It is well adapted to the traditional farming systems of the area. Small-scale farmers, majority of who are rural youths, play a major role in cassava production in Onu-Imo Local Government Area. A number of recommended practices such as timely planting, fertilizer application, timely weeding, herbicide application and planting of stems inclined on ridges which will produce tuberous roots in the same direction to make harvesting easier, have been introduced in an attempt to increase yield per hectare of cassava production (IAR&T, 2005).

Youths have been noted to play a vital role in agricultural production especially in developing countries Nigeria inclusive, where their contribution is paramount. Studies have shown that children and youths contribute significantly in agricultural activities (Ugwoke *et al.*, 2005). Fashina and Okunola (2004), report that all 120 respondents sampled in their study on impact of agricultural programme on food

production in Ondo State were youths and were fully involved in agricultural production activities.

However, because of Western education that our youths acquire every day, there has been a depletion of this youthful labour force in agriculture. There is mass rural urban migration of young people who mostly have no vocational or technical skills looking for scarce white collar jobs (NEEDS, 2004). This migration leads to increased level of the unemployment in urban areas, social ills and vices among others. In Nigeria, data on rural youth participation in agriculture are scarce and in particular on food crops production in the study area (Ekong, 2003). The few studies available on food crops production have focused mainly on the parents of the youths, while the youths who constitute a large proportion of the production force are neglected (Ekong, 2003).

The foregoing therefore, makes it imperative to carry out a study to assess the factors influencing rural youth adoption of cassava recommended production practices in the study area. The broad objective of this study was to assess the factors influencing rural youth adoption of cassava recommended practices in Onu – Imo Local Government Area of Imo State. The specific objectives are to: describe the socio-economic characteristics and institutional variables available for rural youth involved in cassava production activities; Determine the level of adoption of recommended cassava production practices by rural youths in Onu-Imo Local Government Area and their effects; identify the factors influencing rural youth adoption of recommended cassava production practices;

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of rural youths and adoption of recommended cassava production practices.
2. There is no significant relationship between institutional factors and adoption of recommended cassava production practices.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in four communities in Onu-Imo Local Government Area of Imo State. Onu-Imo is one of the 27 Local Government Areas of Imo State. Onu-Imo is in Okigwe Agricultural Zone in Imo State Agricultural Development Project (ADP). Onu-Imo was chosen for this study because it is an agricultural area with high number of youths in agricultural and rural development activities. Onu-Imo had a total population of 54,470 persons in 2006 census figure (NPC, 2006). The projected population figure for 2008 using an annual growth rate of 2.5% is thus, 57,227. The Local Government Area (LGA) has two dominant seasons – rainy and dry seasons. Rain falls between April and October while the dry season starts from November to early March. The Igbo forms the major ethnic group. Christianity and Traditional African Religions are beliefs professed by the people. Onu-Imo falls within the tropical rain forests zone dense forest (FGN, 2004). Agriculture is the mainstay of the economy of the Local Government basically due to the rich arable land suitable for the growth of a wider range of tropical crops. Food crops grown in the area include yam, cassava and maize. The cash crops grown are oil palm and cocoa. The people also keep animals like goats, pigs and poultry. Four communities were randomly selected from the study area. The communities were Okwe, Okwelle, Umuna and Umuduru-egbeaguru. The reasons for the selection were based on observed degree of rurality and the presence of many rural youths, who are engaged in cassava production activities. A village was chosen from each selected community. A list of 1200 rural youths was obtained from Imo State Agricultural Development Programme (IADP) and ten percent of the total number of youths was randomly selected giving a total sample size of 120 youth from all the villages to whom structured questionnaires were administered. The sample frame and sample size for the study in the selected villages are represented in table 1.

Table 1: Sample Frame and Sample Size for Rural Youth in Onu-Imo Local Government Area of Imo State

Local government area	Village	Sample frame	Sample size
Onu-Imo	Okwe	340	34
	Okwelle	260	26
	Umuna	290	29
	Umuduru-egbeaguru	310	31
Total		1200	120

The study made use of both primary and secondary data. The primary data was collected by administering questionnaires to the selected rural youths in January - February, 2008. The data collected were on personal characteristics of the respondents such as age, family size, marital status, years of formal education, sex,

farm size, farming experience, extension contact, leadership status, credit received, and membership of cooperative societies. Other data collected include level of adoption of recommended cassava production practices, yield and income. Secondary data sources were also utilized to provide background information

and other necessary information to achieve some aspects of the study. Such secondary data sources include – journals, proceedings, textbooks, annual reports of FAO, NAERLS and International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA). Descriptive statistics such as tables, percentages, frequency distribution were used to achieve objectives 1, 2, of the study. Multiple regressions were used to achieve objective 3 of the

study. The multiple regression technique was used to estimate the contributions of each independent variable to the dependent variable. The correlation analysis was used to determine the relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Generally, data were organized and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The regression model is specified as follows:

$$Y = a_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + \dots + b_{11}X_{11} + U$$

Where Y: = Adoption of recommended cassava production practices.

X ₁	=	Age of the rural youth (in years)
X ₂	=	Sex, (male = 1, female=2)
X ₃	=	Level of education (in years)
X ₄	=	Marital status (married=1, single=2)
X ₅	=	Farm size (ha)
X ₆	=	House hold size (number)
X ₇	=	Farming experience (in years)
X ₈	=	Leadership status (number)
X ₉	=	Extension contact (number)
X ₁₀	=	Amount of credit received (N)
X ₁₁	=	Membership of cooperative societies (number)
U	=	Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic and Institutional Variables

Socio-economic and institutional variables were considered in this study to elicit their effect on cassava production activities in the study area.

Age of respondents

The ages of the respondents were studied in order to find out the age group mostly involved in cassava production activities. The result in Table 2 reveals that 9.17 percent of the respondents were less than 20 years, while 43.33 percent and 33.33 percent were between 21 – 25 years and 26 – 30 years, respectively. However, 14.17 percent of the respondents were more than 30 years. The findings reveal that majority of the youth were in their productive age, where their energies could be harnessed and utilized for productive venture in agriculture especially cassava production. Thus, it could be concluded that the youths in Onu-Imo Local Government Area were full of life and vigour and can contribute their efforts; physically, mentally and otherwise to boost cassava production in Imo State. Similarly, their relatively young age may make them receptive to new innovations unlike of the older ones who usually expect the maintenance of status quo.

Sex distribution

The study reveals that 81.67 percent of the respondents were male, while 18.33 percent were female (Table 2). According to Adewale *et al.* (2003), gender is no barrier to active involvement in cassava production activities. However, Oladeji *et al.* (2003), observed that it is generally believed that males are often more energetic and could readily be available for

energy demanding jobs like cassava farming. The low percentage of the female youth participating in cassava production could be attributed to the fact that females in the study area usually involved in several other activities outside farming like food vendors, hair dressing, tailoring and petty trading.

Marital status

The finding reveals that 50.83 percent of the respondents were single while 49.17 percent were married as shown in Table 2. Since most of the respondents were single, they could have more time to learn new skills as well as save enough money for cassava production. Since a high percentage of the youth were single and young, they had latent energy in them to go into cassava production without distraction from family members.

Educational status

Table 2 shows that, 5 percent of the respondents had no formal education, while 52.50 percent, 38.33 percent and 4.17 percent had primary, secondary and higher education, respectively. The implication of education in agricultural production according to Arnon (1987), is that education is an important socio-economic variable and a form of human capital for agricultural development. Similarly, Ogunbameru (2001) noted that education will likely enhance the adoption of modern farm technologies by youth and thereby sustaining a virile farming population. Ojukaiye (2001), posits that education is an important socio-economic factor that influences a farmer's decision because of its influence on the farmer's awareness, perception, reception and the adoption of innovation that can bring about increase in production. Since a high percentage of the youths were educated, their education is expected to enhance adoption of

recommended cassava production practices in the study area.

Farm size

The size of the farm cultivated is a function of population pressure, family size and financial background of the farmers. One major characteristic of small-scale farmers is fragmented land holding. The results in Table 4.1 show that 63.33 percent of the respondents farmed on less than one hectare while 33.33 percent and 3.34 percent farmed on between 1-2 hectares and more than two hectares, respectively. Going by Ojuekaiye (2001), classification of farm size of 0.1 hectare to 5.9 hectares as small farms, it then implies that all the respondents were small-scale farmers. This will not allow for meaningful investment and returns to scale on food security.

Household size

Ojuekaiye (2001), defined household size as the number of people eating from on pot. It implies that the consumption unit is also the production unit. Family composition is an important variable in agricultural production because:

- (a) The available work force is obtained from it; and
- (b) size of farm-land is sometimes related to it.

Responses on this variable indicate that 48.33 percent of the respondents had less than 4 people in their family, 45 percent had 4 – 7 people while 7 percent had more than 7 people in their families (Table 4.1). That the respondents had low household size is understandable because they are youths and since they have latent energy, cassava production will increase and food security is assured.

Farm experience

Experience is gained with age. Considering the major occupation of the respondents which is farming, the length of time in farming can be linked with the age of the farmers. As the age increases among the farmers, their years of experience also increase. Table 2 shows that 66.67 percent of the respondents had been in cassava farming for less than 10 years, 20.83 percent and 12.50 percent had been in cassava farming for between 11 – 25 years and more than 25 years respectively. With the above farming experience of the respondents, it is expected that the respondents will be able to make sound decisions as regards resource allocation and management of their cassava farms.

Leadership status

One area where youth contribute greatly is in the area of leadership and politics. Youths have been noted to be less conservative in their nature. This gives credence to their being more receptive to change. According to Adesope *et al.* (2007), if a vacuum has

been noticed, it is almost likely that the youths will speak out and call the attention of the appropriate authorities. For instance, youth leaders go sourcing for credit facilities as well as farm inputs like fertilizers, cassava stem, chemicals and tractor hiring services. Also, youth leaders mobilize their members to draw the attention of the various government authorities as well as non-governmental authorities to attend to their needs. Data results in Table 2 shows that 16.67 percent of the respondents had leadership positions while 83.33 percent of them did not hold leadership positions. This is in order because leaders are usually few while followers are always in the majority. With the current democratic dispensation, youth leaders are not only seen but also heard because the various political associations usually have a youth wing. The more the youth are involved in politics the better for agricultural development which will ensure food security.

Credit received

Capital is an important factor of production. Youths are known to be at disadvantage in getting free and direct access to many sources of credit unlike their parents. Findings indicate that 14.17 percent of the respondents had access to credit for cassava production and majority (85.83 percent) did not have access to credit facilities (Table 2). Writing on credit, FAO (1997), noted that credit should be considered a human right, a basis which allows men and women to face life. Credit is a very strong important factor that is needed to acquire or develop farm enterprise (Ekong, 2003). Its availability could determine the extent of production capacity.

Membership of cooperative societies

Cooperative groups are organized for the promotion of special interest or meet certain needs that cannot be achieved by the individual efforts. They contribute to the dissemination of new ideas, practices and products as well as in sourcing for loan and farm input. Findings revealed that 19.17 percent of the respondents were members of cooperative society, while 80.83 percent of the respondents did not belong to any cooperative society (Table 4.1). This agrees with the earlier findings why majority of the respondents did not have access to credit facilities. This also could determine the extent of production capacity.

Extension contacts

Agricultural extension service constitutes a driving force for any agricultural development. The relationship between agricultural extension agent and the farmer is an important determinant in improving yield of cassava as well as in ensuring food security. The result of the findings revealed that 86.66 percent of the respondents had contact with extension agents between one to two times from January, 2007 to February, 2008. Seven percent had contact more than two times, while 6.67 percent did not have contact with the extension agents in the growing season prior to the

time the study was conducted. There is need for more cassava production. visits of extension workers to enhance increase in

Table 2: Respondents Socio-economic and Institutional Variables

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age in years		
≤20	11	9.17
21 – 25	52	43.33
26 – 30	40	33.33
>30	17	14.17
Sex		
Male	98	81.67
Female	22	18.33
Marital status		
Single	61	50.83
Married	59	49.17
Educational status		
No formal education	6	5.00
Primary education	63	52.50
Secondary education	46	38.33
Higher education	5	4.17
Farm size(ha)		
<1	76	63.33
1 – 2	40	33.33
> 2	4	3.34
Household size		
<4	58	48.33
4 - 7	54	45.00
>7	8	6.67
Farming experience(years)		
≤ 10	80	66.67
11 – 25	25	20.83
> 25	15	12.50
Leadership status		
Member	20	16.67
Non-member	100	83.33
Credit		
Access to credit	17	14.17
Non-access to credit	103	85.83
Cooperative societies		
Member	23	19.17
Non-member	97	80.83
Extension contact		
No contact	8	6.67
1 – 2	104	86.66
> 2	8	6.67
Total	120	100

Level of Adoption of Recommended Cassava Production Practices

Adoption in this study was based on the number of technologies constantly used by the respondents. The adoption level represents the number of respondents using the practices as a percentage of the total number of the respondents studied (Ojo, 2009).

Figure 1 shows that 40 percent of the respondents adopted planting of healthy stem cut at mid point, 45 percent adopted planting time while 65 percent adopted plant spacing, 69 percent adopted planting on ridges at an angle while 49 percent and 73 percent adopted weeding time and fertilizer application respectively. Fertilizer application has the highest adoption (73 percent) level. This can be seen as

evident in the yield. This agrees with Ikechukwu (1990), who reported that proper application of fertilizer has been described as an essential prerequisite for the realization of increase crop yield as well as for restoration and maintenance of soil fertility.

Planting of healthy stem cuttings which are cut at mid point recorded the lowest level of adoption among the respondents (40 percent). This could be attributed to the fact that cassava farmers in the study area still use the traditional method of planting stem cut below midpoint. Weeding and plant spacing recorded 49 percent and 65 percent level of adoption respectively. These could be attributed to old management techniques employed by the farmers to control pest infestation and therefore does not deviate from the practices that rural youth have known

Figure I: Distribution of Respondents According to Level of Adoption

Legend: 1 = planting healthy stems cut at midpoint, 2 = planting time, 3 = plant spacing, 4 = planting on ridges, 5 = weeding time, 6 = fertilizer application.

Factors Influencing Rural Youth Adoption of Recommended Cassava Production Practices: Correlation and Regression Analyses

The Correlation and Regression analyses were used to estimate the socio-economic and institutional variables influencing cassava production in the study area. The results of these analyses were based on the study's hypotheses and they are highlighted below.

HYPOTHESIS 1

The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics of rural youth and adoption of recommended cassava production practices. The socio-economic characteristics studied include age, sex, marital status, education, farm size, household size, farming experience, leadership status, extension contact and membership of cooperatives.

The findings show that household size was positively but weakly correlated ($r = 0.136$) to adoption of recommended cassava production practices at 5 percent level of significance. The correlation analysis also shows that age (0.205) was positively correlated with adoption of recommended cassava production practices. The household size (0.136) could be said to be significant because the farmers were youth and youth have relatively smaller families compared to older farmers and this leads them to take more risk (of adopting new practices) than the older farmers. This agrees with Adesope (2006), who opined that youth are less conservative in their nature and are more receptive to change. Other socio-economic variables like sex (.045), marital status (.205), education (.068), farm size (.095), farming experience (.136), leadership experience (.067), membership of

cooperative society (.107) and credit (.032) were not significant to the adoption of recommended cassava production practices. However, extension contact, yield and income were significant. Thus the null hypothesis was therefore rejected as there was significant relationship

HYPOTHESIS 2

The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between the institutional variables and adoption of recommended cassava production practices. The institutional variables considered included extension contact, membership of co-operative society and amount of credit received. The findings of the correlation analysis shows that extension contact was positive and weakly correlated. The positive correlation implies that the rural youth have relatively good amount of contact with extension agents.

The result of the regression analysis in Table 4 is in line with the findings of the correlation analysis. From Table 4 extension contact was significant at 1 percent level of probability. Agricultural extension agents are important for transferring agricultural practices to the farmers. Extension services serve as an effective channel through which information is passed to the farmers. They also enlighten farmers on the sources of inputs for sustained use of new technologies. Extension agents play a major role in the dissemination of latest agricultural practices. The result of the study shows that the extension agents had frequent contact with the rural youth. This agrees with the findings of Atala (1984) who confirmed the important role of extension agents in the diffusion and adoption of an innovation. Membership of cooperative society from the result of correlation analysis shows

that there was a positive and weak relationship with adoption of recommended cassava production practices. The regression analysis also revealed that membership of cooperative society was not significant to the adoption of recommended cassava production practices at both 1 percent and 5 percent level of probability. This could be because majority of the rural youth do not belong to any cooperative society as captured in Table 4. Participation in voluntary social organization such as cooperative society provides farmers with useful information, latest technology and actual learning experience in agricultural production. It is expected that membership of cooperative societies should have positive effect on adoption. However, no significant relationship was found in this study. This agrees with the findings of Ojo (2009) who discovered that belonging to a cooperative society was not significant with adoption of recommended cassava

production practices. This finding is at variance with the study of Deji (2005), who found membership of cooperative societies as a predictive factor of adoption behaviour of farmers.

Amount of credit was not significant with adoption of recommended cassava production practices in the study area. This could be due to the fact that about 86 percent of the respondents do not have access to credit facilities as was seen in Table 4. This agrees with the findings of Atala et al. (1992) who also found insignificant correlation between amount of credit and adoption. The insignificant correlation between credit and adoption could be due to misuse of credit and the fact that only few respondents obtained credit. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected as there was significant relationship between extension contact and adoption of recommended cassava production practices.

Table 4: Regression Coefficients of Factors Influencing Adoption of Recommended Cassava Production Practices by Rural Youths

Variables	Regression Coefficients	Standard Error	t-value	Level of Significance
Constant	-2.301	2.113	-1.089	0.279
Age	0.183	0.170	1.078	0.283 ^{NS}
Sex	0.019	0.090	0.211	0.833 ^{NS}
Marital status	0.185	0.135	1.373	0.173 ^{NS}
Education	0.015	0.098	0.153	0.879 ^{NS}
Farm size	-0.023	0.088	-0.260	0.795 ^{NS}
Household size	-0.306	0.133	-2.308	0.023 ^{**}
Farming experience	-0.143	0.152	-0.939	0.350 ^{NS}
Leadership status	0.037	0.142	0.260	0.795 ^{NS}
Extension contact	0.328	0.102	3.222	0.002 [*]
Cooperative membership	-0.226	0.200	-1.129	0.262 ^{NS}
Amount of credit	0.084	0.144	0.585	0.560 ^{NS}
Yield	0.453	0.122	3.723	0.000 [*]
Income	0.385	0.095	4.034	0.000 [*]

* = Significant at 1% level of probability

** = Significant at 5% level of probability

^{NS} = Not significant

Coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) = 0.292

Adjusted coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) = 0.205

F = 3.359

Conclusion

The study shows that 43.33 percent of the respondents were in their active age (21 – 25 years). The implication is that the respondents were young, strong, active and very energetic and were very likely to ensure adequate food security for their families and Nigeria in general. The respondents were mostly small-scale farmers with fragmented holdings. About 95 percent of the respondents had formal education. The implication is that it will hasten the adoption of farm technologies. Only 14.17 percent of the respondents had access to credit and 19.17 percent were members of co-operative societies. Some of the socio-economic and institutional attributes of the respondents were found to have negative effects, which were implicitly not conducive for increased output. Objective two determined the level of adoption of recommended cassava production practices by rural youth in the study area. It was discovered that 40

percent of the respondents adopted planting of healthy stem cut at midpoint, 45 percent adopted planting time while 65 percent adopted plant spacing. Sixty-nine percent adopted planting on ridges at an angle while 49 percent and 73 percent adopted weeding time and fertilizer application, respectively.

Objective three identified the factors influencing rural youth' adoption of recommended cassava production practices. The result of correlation and regression analysis revealed that among the socio-economic characteristics, household size was positive and significant to adoption of recommended cassava production practices at 5% level of significance. Extension contact was the institutional variable that was significant to adoption of recommended cassava production practices at 1 percent level of significance. Yield and income were also positively correlated and significant to adoption of recommended cassava production practices at 1 percent level of significance..

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